

Evaluating Kieran Egan's Rationale for Curriculum Reform

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Introduction

From his defense of rote learning as a legitimate teaching option to his condemnation of empirical research, Kieran Egan frequently challenges longstanding assumptions about education. These various criticisms of commonly held assumptions about education are intended to pave the way for the curriculum reform he envisions. In this article, we evaluate Egan's major critiques of education, and consider whether these analyses constitute appropriate justification for curriculum change. We examine Egan's views on stage development theory, incompatibilities in curricular objectives, progressive education practices, and evidence-based research. Following our review, we suggest that although Egan's critiques of progressive education and curriculum incompatibilities are unconvincing, his concerns about stage development theory and empirical research appear warranted. We also suggest that many of the pedagogical imperatives Egan advances are valuable regardless of his challenges to mainstream education practice.

Stage Development Theory: Egan vs. Piaget

In a 1983 publication entitled "What Does Piaget's Theory Describe?" Egan shares an experience that transformed his previous assumptions about teaching and learning. While teaching an educational psychology graduate course, Egan reflected on the tenability of the Piagetian stage development model so influential in schools and teacher education programs. Based on his personal experience with children, something seemed terribly amiss with the claim that young children progress as they age in linear fashion toward greater levels of cognitive capability. Egan (2002) explains the problem as follows: "The view does not allow for any possibility except a gradually improving mind. This progressive view hides any irregularities, backtracking or convolutions of our development and cannot accommodate the possibility that young children are intellectually superior to adults in any way" (p. 102).

The considerable evidence Egan compiled in the 1983 article mounts a convincing case against stage development theory. There is, of course, the predictable mention of Piaget's experimental study group, comprised exclusively of children from upper middle class Geneva backgrounds. Since the children shared common cultural and educational experiences, it is unremarkable, if not predictable, that they also shared certain knowledge, as well as mutual linguistic and cognitive abilities. Egan contends that Piaget mistook the descriptive elements of his observation for the prescriptive model of child development he adopted. In other words, the culture, knowledge and understanding acquired via social experience were incorrectly construed by Piaget as the product of

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innate cognitive structures that unfolded in parallel with physical development.

From the Piagetian perspective, cognitive development is largely a function of the organism, with the environment playing only a minor role. Such a view runs contrary to Egan's contention that culture is the predominant influence on learning and development. Indeed, when faced with a host of environmentally induced instances of developmental unevenness in performance, Piaget himself admitted he could not explain them (Piaget, 1971, p. 11).

Egan also raises the problem for Piaget that when children are formally instructed in competencies above their theorized stage level, many can successfully complete the task in question. For example, children initially unable to understand the concept of conservation may fully grasp the idea after guided instruction. If a definitive cognitive stage within the organism actually determines learning ability, as Piaget proposed, then merely teaching children about the concept should prove inadequate in enhancing their understanding of conservation.

Perhaps the most compelling criticism of Piaget's theory involves Egan's experience of children not as cognitively inferior versions of adults, but as dynamic intellectual sponges absorbing tremendous quantities of information as they learn language and related concepts demanding precisely the type of abstract thinking that Piaget's theory disallows. Moreover, the imagination, central to Egan's pedagogical agenda, is a cognitive ability he deems far more active in children than in adults. Hence, according to Egan, human development is not some linear process of cognitive growth as Piaget contends, but rather a series of gains, convolutions and losses as we move from childhood to adulthood.

Egan points out that as a result of Piagetian assumptions, teachers too often hold a tacit perspective of children that is rooted in recapitulation theory, limiting children's academic challenges. Herbert Spencer introduced recapitulation theory into education when he suggested that the education of the child should reflect the historical development of humankind. From this perspective, the developing child recapitulates all the stages of development of our species, from the primitive and simple to the civilized and complex (Egan, 2002, p. 27). When children are understood as incomplete versions of adults, Piaget's theory becomes a series of hypotheses about what children are unable to achieve. Rather than encouraging young learners to aim toward greater academic heights, teachers following Piagetian dictums may adopt lower expectations and, accordingly, retard the intellectual and academic growth of students. Egan also claims that teachers pay a tremendous professional price for adopting Piagetian assumptions, since when children fail to learn instructors are often blamed for not teaching to the appropriate level of stage development (Egan, 2002, p. 51).

The problems Egan cited with Piagetian theory eventually led him to investigate the work of Russian psychologist Lev Vygotsky, whose wealth of contributions to education was only posthumously recognized. In his seminal work *Mind in Society* (1978), Vygotsky, a social constructivist, argues that human development, rather than being a function of innate cognitive structures, is actually the product of acquired cultural tools, or language

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operating in conjunction with socially shared knowledge and understanding. An extension of this position, Vygotsky's *zone of proximal development*, suggests that student learning is constrained only by the level of current achievement plus the potential level of achievement realized with the assistance of competent guided instruction. Egan's rejection of Piaget's stage development theory—an idea he actually traces to Rousseau's *Emile* (1979)¹—and his subsequent embracing of Vygotsky is most visible in Egan's *The Educated Mind: How Cognitive Tools Shape our Understanding* (1998).

Cultural Tools and Education

Egan begins *The Educated Mind* (1998) by reviewing the three central aims he claims dominate the organization of public school curricula. These aims are the socializing responsibility of education to inculcate children with the norms, values and beliefs of the prevailing culture; the penchant for improving what Egan refers to as “critical thinking,” or the “search for truth” through rational orientation he traces to Plato and the Allegory of the Cave; and, finally, the desire for children to develop their inherent potential “naturally,” another aim that Egan links to Rousseau's *Emile*. Egan argues that these three orientations dominate discussions about educational aims, but actually work in opposition to each other, thereby creating conflicting and incoherent curriculum objectives:

In the case of the modern school, three distinctive aims have attended its development. It is expected to serve as a significant agency in socializing the young, to teach particular forms of knowledge that will bring about a realistic and rational view of the world, and to help realize the unique potential of each child. These goals are generally taken to be consistent with one another, somewhat overlapping, and mutually supportive. However ... the more we work to achieve one of the schools' aims, the more difficult it becomes to achieve the others. (Egan, 1998, p. 10)

In Egan's view, the fundamental incompatibilities generate chronic pedagogical confusions that impede student learning and ultimately prevent teachers from achieving any single curriculum aim. However, some of the incompatibilities Egan identifies misrepresent the corresponding curriculum orientations.

Egan (1998) argues that the child-centered, natural learning approach rooted in Rousseau's philosophy of education is fundamentally incompatible with the socializing responsibility of schools: “They are incompatible because socializing has a distinct end in view and is a shaping, homogenizing, narrowing process toward that end, whereas supporting the fullest development of student potential involves releasing students to explore and discover their uniqueness” (p. 22). Egan also claims that integrating the socializing objective of education with the “search for truth/rational” curriculum orientation is similarly incoherent. He argues that designing school programs to achieve both the socializing and critical goals of education inevitably generates curricular and pedagogical confusion: “The homogenizing aim of socialization, which is to reproduce in each student a particular set of beliefs, conventions, commitments, norms of behavior,

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and values is necessarily at odds with a process that aims to show their hollowness and inadequacy” (p. 18). However, Egan’s conviction that socializing and critical curricular aims are necessarily incompatible reflects a conceptual misunderstanding. His view is predicated on the assumption that social values will be deemed *ipso facto* “hollow and inadequate” upon student critique, and on a contestable, narrow, Durkheim-driven conception of socialization. In *The Rules of the Sociological Method* (1958), Durkheim advanced a biological analogy for the study and explanation of society. Individuals within society are like cells within the body. The cells depend on the smooth and uninterrupted functioning of other cells and organs that ensure the survival of the organism. A well functioning society, then, becomes one based on social and normative cohesion rather than one founded on perpetual critique.

The problem with Durkheim’s structural functionalism is that complete emphasis on social cohesion ignores the normative particularities of a given society. Indeed, one need not search far to discover historical examples where an efficient and morally united society was neither ethically acceptable nor democratic. It’s a serious problem for structural functionalism, and one that encouraging democratic social critique from students is designed to redress.

There is no obvious reason why social beliefs, norms and conventions would be necessarily deemed inappropriate following student examination, and there is no reasonable explanation why socialization ought to include the uncritical inculcation of norms and beliefs in students. In fact, a primary socializing responsibility of schools within a democracy is promoting the full political participation of students by encouraging social critique and, when necessary, inviting some measure of structural transformation. This need not be a disruptive pedagogical objective, but rather can be a reflective, formative and purely educative one. For example, Henry Giroux (2003) argues that the moral dimension of democratic education “means giving students the knowledge and skills to enable them to interrogate and defend the values and norms that are crucial to recognizing anti-democratic forms of power and expanding the operations of freedom and democracy” (p. 94). Contrary to Egan’s contention, then, it is perfectly coherent for teachers to convey prevailing social beliefs and conventions to students, while still subjecting them to the light beyond the cave. Democratic socialization is conceptually and practically distinct from indoctrination precisely because the former invites criticism and change while the latter obviates these possibilities.

In spite of this difficulty with *The Educated Mind’s* rationale for curriculum reform, Egan’s cognitive tools approach offers a sophisticated alternative to popular thinking about education. He describes the concept of cognitive tools in the following fashion:

cognitive tools are the things that enable our brains to do cultural work. Our brains, like those of any animal, are responsible for an array of physiological and social work. But we have also amassed that external symbolic material that constitutes our culture. As we learn features of our cultural inheritance, the brain is provided with the tools that enable it to realize its various capacities. Alone, no one learns to speak, to read and write, or to think with theoretic abstractions.

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These potentials of human brains are actualized only by the brain learning, and learning to use, particular pieces from our cultural storehouse. Culture, as it were, programs the brain. (Egan, 2008)

Although he rejects *recapitulation theory* as implied in the views of Herbert Spencer and Jean Piaget, Egan's cultural tools model reflects a similar approach in which progressive historical periods parallel various types of understanding. Egan's cultural tools include mythic, romantic, philosophic, ironic and somatic understanding, and each tool contributes to learning by affording students different ways to describe their experience.

As we have indicated, recapitulation theory suggests that the development of the individual mimics the development of civilization, with the latter being viewed in a progressive linear sense. Consistent with this idea, mythic understanding connects student learning to the earliest forms of explanatory beliefs about human experience. Mythic understanding includes learning about ideas and concepts through binaries, metaphor, abstract thinking, imagination and fantasy. Romantic understanding embraces the limits of human knowledge, and draws upon our powerful personal relationships to environmental forces and influences: "Central to Romantic understanding is a sense of an autonomous self and a relatedly autonomous reality" (Egan, 1998, p. 22). Philosophic understanding incorporates many of the tools of logical analysis, science, and explanation supporting metaphysical structures or grand narratives such as Marxism, religion and evolutionary theory. Egan suggests that these narratives are most likely epistemologically flawed, a suspicion shaping the foundation for the ultimate cultural tool, ironic understanding.

Ironic understanding, the apparent pinnacle of Egan's cultural tool inventory, emerges from the alleged failure of philosophic understanding, and by extension of science, to deliver an epistemological foundation for objective knowledge. Embodying many of the insights offered by Richard Rorty's pragmatism, ironic understanding appreciates the limits of human cognition and adopts a skeptical if nevertheless pragmatic attitude toward truth. Rorty (1989) has argued that "truth" is what is good or useful for us to believe. Ironic understanding, similarly, assumes that attempts to identify an objective reality accessible to humans are most probably doomed to failure. Finally, somatic understanding operates at a pre- or non-linguistic level, interacting with and shaping the other categories of understanding. It includes understanding of basic human drives such as hunger and sex, and the emotional responses these feelings precipitate.

Flaws and Virtues of Progressive Education

Egan's attack on conventional thinking about education and the legacy it follows is intensified in *Getting it Wrong From the Beginning: Our Progressivist Inheritance From Herbert Spencer, John Dewey and Jean Piaget* (2002). Egan begins his analysis in this work with the assumption that schools as presently designed represent a huge educational failure. The actual evidence offered to support the claim may be thin and anecdotal, but Egan would have little difficulty building a cohort of subscribers to his view. The overarching theme in the book may be summarized as follows: Contemporary education

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pursues flawed progressivist practices that hinder rather than help student academic development. Egan reiterates his claim that curriculum should cultivate student mastery over various cognitive tools: “Understanding how these tools shape our learning can give us a better set of principles for improving the effectiveness of students’ learning than anything progressivism can provide” (Egan, 2002, p. 75). *Getting It Wrong from the Beginning* challenges many progressivist pedagogical practices, but overlooks the important democratic dispositions fostered through the progressive approach to schooling. Indeed, there are two distinct strands to the progressive education movement. One is the scientific strand Egan attacks, while the other is the student-centered strand concerned with fostering democratic dispositions that he ignores.

Egan argues that many of the misguided progressivist ideas about teaching and learning originate with the pseudo-scientific theories of 19th-century British philosopher Herbert Spencer. A leading proponent of Lamarckian evolutionary theory in the mid-19th century, Spencer’s reputation briefly rivaled that of Charles Darwin. Lamarckian theory incorrectly held that organisms changed as a result of use and disuse of body parts that were incorporated into subsequent generations of the species. For example, the long necks possessed by Giraffes supposedly resulted from continual stretching to obtain leaves and twigs located in high trees. Spencer was most recognized during the period for applying survival-of-the-fittest principles to philosophy, psychology, and the general investigation of society. Although he is typically remembered in contemporary academic circles for his controversial support of social Darwinian assumptions, he also devoted significant philosophical energy to improving education based on “scientific” principles (Spencer, 1928; Spencer, 1966).

Egan claims that many of the education principles Spencer developed influenced the subsequent work of Dewey and Piaget. Although he admits that establishing causal connections between historically related ideas is difficult, Egan provides plenty of circumstantial evidence to support his thesis. He speculates that progressivist scholars refused to acknowledge their indebtedness to Spencer because of the latter’s morally offensive positions on race and social class. Spencer assumed that poor people were biologically inferior to wealthy people, and that any attempt to improve the former’s circumstances through education merely wasted available resources. His distasteful remedy for addressing social disparity discouraged poor people from procreating. Spencer’s objectionable beliefs about race and class eventually fell from grace, but his ideas about education endured and, as Egan points out, attained considerable academic influence.

One especially influential principle developed by Spencer maintains that children’s learning begins with simple ideas and progressively advances to more complex conceptions. This remains a widely accepted view in education and is most notably reflected in Piaget’s claim that young children are primarily concrete thinkers who only later acquire the cognitive capacity for abstract thought. According to Egan, this principle actually originated with an inference Spencer drew from Karl Ernst von Baer’s cosmological speculation that humans “are part of an immense process that moves inexorably from the homogeneous to the heterogeneous” (Egan, 2002, p. 26). This

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hypothesis collapsed with the introduction of Helmholtz's second law of thermodynamics, but its influence on education endured. In the mid-19th century, Helmholtz theorized that the universe is actually moving toward increased homogeneity rather than toward greater degrees of complexity, thereby undermining the premise supporting Spencer's simple-to-complex postulation on learning.

Spencer also suggested that rote learning renders "the pupil a mere recipient of other's ideas" (Egan, 2002, p. 17). Although the rejection of rote learning remains a common feature of contemporary teacher education programs, Egan suggests that this approach embodies a grave misunderstanding about how learning and knowledge acquisition influence human experience. Memorizing a Romantic poem by Wordsworth or the "quality of mercy" passage from Shakespeare's *The Merchant of Venice* affords students more than an accumulated pool of inert information. Such learning shapes character by influencing perceptions about experience, or by potentially modifying entire worldviews. As Egan observes, knowledge acquired during rote learning often becomes part of our "living tissue" (Egan, 2002, p. 68).

Egan's work on learning and education is rich with insight. For instance, he points out that the pervasive influence of psychology on current curriculum development is another legacy of Spencer's belief that science offers the optimum method to enrich learning. Apart from advancing the ubiquitous critique that social science methods are unable to grasp the complexity of human experience, Egan believes that most claims emerging from educational research amount to analytic propositions. Analytic propositions are trivial tautologies where the predicate is contained within the subject (i.e. *all bachelors are unmarried men*). His criticism of empirical research in education is based on an article published by Jan Smedslund in the *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology* in 1979. Smedslund argued that the empirical generalizations emerging from social science research merely explicate the analytical relationships between ordinary language concepts:

The theoretical analysis contains elements of both the analytic and the arbitrary, but neither is overtly acknowledged. The analytic element is incompatible with the aspiration to empirical testing, and the arbitrary element is incompatible with the aspiration to generality and timelessness. These latent contradictions can remain generally undiscovered only as long as the standards for theoretical precision remain at their current low level. Meanwhile, the façade of scientific respectability is only maintained by the advanced technology for data gathering and analysis. (Smedslund, 1979, p. 140)

Thus, the truly empirical findings of social science research are arbitrary, or non-generalizable, while the generalizable propositions are simply logical necessities.

Egan employs the U.S. National Research Council (NRC) funded study *How People Learn* to illustrate his point. This well funded study sought to provide a research base for best practices in education that would supposedly improve classroom teaching. The somewhat banal findings that emerged from the extensive "research" included: "To

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develop competence in an area of inquiry, students must (a) have a deep foundation of factual knowledge, (b) understand facts and ideas in the context of a conceptual framework, and (c) organize knowledge in ways that facilitate retrieval and application” (Donovan, Bransford, & Pelligrino, 1999, cited in Egan, 2002, p. 166-167). Egan correctly points out that these so-called principles of best practice are simply *definitions* of what is meant by competence within an area of inquiry since individuals lacking these abilities would not be considered competent within their respective fields.

Egan generally mounts a convincing case against the pseudo-scientific principles of Herbert Spencer and many of the progressivist pedagogical practices they occasioned. But the contribution of progressivist principles to contemporary education cannot be completely dismissed on this basis alone. Much of Dewey’s most valuable and influential scholarship such as that in *Democracy and Education* (1916) and *The Public and Its Problems* (1927) emphasizes the political relationship between democratically structured education, student agency, and participatory democratic citizenship. In *Democracy and Education*, for example, Dewey outlines the social importance of the democratic dispositions fostered through a properly structured education:

An undesirable society ... is one which internally and externally sets up barriers to free intercourse and communication of experience. A society which makes provision for participation in its good of all its members on equal terms and which secures flexible readjustment of its institutions through interaction of the different forms of associated life is in so far democratic. Such a society must have a type of education which gives individuals a personal interest in social relationships and control, and the habits of mind which secure social changes without introducing disorder. (1916, p. 49)

Indeed, the advocacy of generating democratic dispositions in students and identifying corresponding pedagogical practices to achieve that objective may comprise progressivism’s most important legacy to both education and society. Unfortunately, this central element of progressivism is missing from Egan’s analysis.

Summary and Conclusion

Egan’s ideas on the human imagination and his recent Learning in Depth (LiD) project (2013) hold considerable promise for teachers and educators seeking alternatives to mainstream pedagogical approaches: “Learning in Depth’ is a simple though radical innovation in curriculum and instruction designed to ensure that all students become experts about something during their school years. Each child is given a particular topic to learn about through her or his whole school career, in addition to the usual curriculum, and builds a personal portfolio on the topic” (Egan, 2013). Furthermore, Egan’s challenge to Piaget and corresponding support of Vygotsky, as well as his critique of education research, constitute tremendously important insights on mainstream thinking about education. We are less convinced that the curriculum aims he identifies as fundamentally incompatible are necessarily so, and we worry that his strategy embracing various forms of cultural understanding adopts the same hierarchical recapitulation

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assumptions he criticizes in Spencer's views. More generally, though, there is abundant intellectual fodder in Egan's scholarship on education and, at the very least, we hope this article inspires teachers, researchers and students to investigate, support, challenge and revise his rich collection of ideas about teaching and learning.²

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Notes

¹ In *Emile*, Rousseau divides human development into five distinct stages and prescribed different learning approaches for each stage. He also argues, in a manner that foreshadows Piaget's approach, that children should not confront excessive expectations in their learning.

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